

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON DRONES & TECHNOLOGY APPLIED TO THE CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE EUROPEAN SME

8TH JUNE 2018
UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA

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SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

- Assoc Prof. Virginia Santamarina | UPV
- Miguel Rosa | CEO, Aerotools
- Gavin O'Brien | Founder & CEO, Clearhead
- Vadim Vermeiren | COO, Pozyx
- Assoc. Prof. María de Miguel Molina | UPV
- Assoc. Prof. José Luis Poza Luján | UPV
- Assoc. Prof. Blanca de Miguel Molina | UPV
- Assoc. Prof. Montserrat Pareja Eastaway | Universitat de Barcelona
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- Assoc. Prof. Rafael Boix | UPV

VENUE

Plenary session: Auditorium Alfons Roig, Faculty of Fine Arts
Universitat Politècnica de València. Building 3N. Camino de Vera s/n

Demonstration session: The Príncipe Felipe Science Museum
The City of Arts and Sciences. Av Profesor López Piñero, 7, 46013 Valencia

REGISTER at [AIRT.EU/WORKSHOP](https://airt.eu/workshop)

The capacity will be limited due to a demonstration in the second part of the event.
The registration fee is 35€ until 1st of May, and 70€ after 1st of May, and includes:

- Attendance certificate
- Transport between both event venues (UPV - CAC)
- Two coffee breaks and one lunch break
- The publication of the minutes "Drones & Technology Applied to the Creative Industries. Innovative Strategies for the European SMEs" by Springer

PLENARY SESSION

- 08:30 - 09:00** Registration
- 09:00 - 09:15** Opening ceremony
D. José E. Capilla Romá, Vice-president for Research & Innovation, UPV
- 09:15 - 09:45** **Creative industries in H2020: EC programmes and new calls**
Marcel Watelet, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology - Data Applications & Creativity, European Commission
- 09:45 - 10:30** **Past, present and future of drones: a field full of opportunities**
J. Ramiro Martínez de Dios, Full Professor, Department of Automation and Systems Engineering, University of Seville
- 10:30 - 11:00** **Current and future issues related to the indoor drones' European regulation**
María de Miguel Molina, AiRT project Dissemination Manager, UPV

11:00 - 11:30 COFFEE BREAK

- 11:30 - 12:00** **AIRT Project as an example of responsible innovation**
Virginia Santamarina, AiRT Project Coordinator, UPV
- 12:00 - 12:30** **The positioning system as the key feature for indoor drones**
Vadim Vermeiren, COO, Pozyx
- 12:30 - 13:00** **What are we doing with drones in the creative industries?**
Gavin O'Brien, Founder & CEO, Clearhead
- 13:00 - 13:30** **The challenge of innovation in Europa within the creative industries'**
Verónica Buey Cieslak, Deputy Cluster Manager at Madrid ICT-Audiovisual Cluster

13:30 - 14:00 NETWORKING LUNCH BREAK

- 14:00 - 14:30** **How do creative industries innovate?**
Montserrat Pareja Eastaway, Associate Professor, Department of Economic Theory, University of Barcelona
- 14:30 - 15:00** **How the European drones' market is changing and how we envision the future**
Miguel Rosa, AiRT project Exploitation Manager, CEO, AeroTools
- 15:00 - 15:30** **From robotics to creativity. Knowledge cross-seeding effects for innovation and tech-transfer projects**
José Luis Poza Luján, AiRT project Technical Manager, UPV
- 15:30 - 16:00** **Drones' impact on the creative industries field and how they can affect other industries**
Blanca de Miguel Molina, AiRT project Exploitation Manager, UPV

16:00 - 16:30 COFFEE BREAK

DEMONSTRATION SESSION

- 16:30 - 17:00** Bus shuttle to The Príncipe Felipe Science Museum
- 17:00 - 17:45** Demonstration session at The Príncipe Felipe Science Museum
- 17:45 - 18:00** Closing ceremony